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ABSTRACT

Throughout the development of mankind, language and culture have been closely related to each other. Language is not only a means of communication, but also a social phenomenon that reflects the thinking, worldview, values, and history of the people. Culture, on the other hand, is manifested through the life, lifestyle, customs, art, moral standards, and so on of members of society. This article discusses the interrelationship between language and culture, their role in the life of society, and their mutual influence.

Language and culture are one of the most important pillars of human civilization. As a result of their unity, the national psyche, cultural heritage and social consciousness are formed. Therefore, attention to language and culture, their protection serve the future of any nation.

Language is a mirror of culture. Language is the most important cultural wealth of every nation. Through language, the people pass on their history, ancient traditions, customs and spiritual world from generation to generation. For example, numerous proverbs, sayings, folk tales, songs and epics in the Uzbek language play an incomparable role in the formation of national consciousness and culture.

Language also actively participates in all spheres of culture - art, literature, religion, customs and rituals. For example, prayers, solemn poems or games recited at wedding ceremonies strengthen culture through language. Therefore, preserving and developing the language is, in fact, preserving and preserving national culture.

Also, through language, one can study the stages of historical development of a people and understand how culture has changed. Ancient words, phrases, and dialects preserved in the language archive are a valuable source for historians and cultural scholars.

The specific aspects of culture are also clearly visible in the German language. For example, German is a very precise language, in which the strict arrangement of words, complex word formation rules, and the widespread use of formal style reflect the German people's commitment to discipline, accuracy, and tradition. In particular, German fairy tales (collections of the Brothers Grimm) played an important role in transmitting culture to generations through this language.

For example, in the Uzbek language there is a proverb: 'a guest is greater than his father.' This expression means that hospitality is an integral part of the culture of our people. In German, 'Gastfreundschaft geht durch den Magen'

Culture is reflected in language. Culture cannot fail to influence language. The cultural level, social values, and moral standards of a particular society are reflected through language. For example, let's take expressions of respect in the Uzbek language: expressions such as "siz", "janoblari", "muhtaram", "hurmatli" are a manifestation of the high respect and etiquette culture in society for elders, guests, and others.

Also, the moral criteria existing in culture are reflected in language. This forms the culture of interaction of people. Among the Uzbek folk proverbs, expressions such as "Til bilan dos orttir, kilich bilan dushman", "Shirin so'z - jon ozig'i" once again prove the place of language in culture.

Lexical and grammatical features in the language are also formed under the influence of culture. For example, Arabic and Persian words introduced under the influence of religious culture have enriched the cultural layer of the Uzbek language. Today, English words are introduced through technological culture.

Respect and formality play a large role in German culture, which is also clearly felt in the language. For example, when talking to people who do not know German well or are in a formal setting, the form 'Sie' (you) is used. This expression expresses the culture of interaction and respect between people. Also, the expression 'Ordnung muss sein' (There must be order) is widespread among Germans, which expresses their cultural worldview.

Phrases and proverbs that have become part of the language say a lot about culture. For example, Uzbeks consider 'A good word is the food of the soul', which shows how important the word is in upbringing and culture. The Germans say 'Worte sind wie Pfeile' (Words are like arrows), which means that words have power and should be used with caution.

The role of language and culture in the context of globalization

Today's globalization process is having a great impact on language and culture. As a result of the widespread spread of world languages, small national languages and cultures are at risk of losing their status. In this regard, each nation should pay great attention to preserving and developing its national language and culture.

Along with globalization, intercultural dialogue is intensifying. Although this allows for mutual enrichment and the adoption of new ideas, in some cases it can also lead to the loss of national characteristics. Therefore, it is necessary to strengthen the national language and values to protect against cultural apathy.

The language policy pursued in Uzbekistan is yielding positive results in this regard. Strengthening the status of the Uzbek language as a state language and ensuring its widespread use in science, technology, education and other fields serves to develop national culture.

In Germany, great attention is paid to the preservation of language and culture. German language and literature lessons are mandatory in educational institutions. At the same time, the teaching of foreign languages also serves to expand intercultural dialogue. Germany works through the Goethe Institutes to popularize its culture on the global stage, which contributes to the international recognition of the German language and culture.

Under the influence of globalization, English terms are widely used in the German language. For example, words such as 'Handy' (mobile phone), 'downloaden' (download) show how modern culture and technology affect the language. Similarly, words such as 'computer', 'internet', 'online' are actively used in the Uzbek language. These circumstances indicate that language and culture are in constant motion.

Conclusion. Language and culture are two important social phenomena that complement and rely on each other. They are an important factor in the development of society and are of incomparable importance in preserving the identity of any people. Therefore, the development of language and preservation of culture is the sacred duty of everyone, especially the younger generation.

By instilling a love for language and culture in the younger generation, we ensure that they grow up as patriotic, proud and spiritually rich people. Therefore, reforms in this area must be permanent.

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